

CLINICAL PUZZEL

Clinico-radiological quiz: Hypoplastic Rib

Ambika Sharma*

ABSTRACT

A thirty-year-old male, nonsmoker, presented with complaints of acute onset moderately severe intensity left sided chest pain after lifting heavy weight. A chest radiograph was taken (Figure 1).

Spot the radiological abnormality?

Answer to Clinico-Radiological Quiz

HYPOPLASTIC LEFT 4TH RIB.

A thirty-year-old male, nonsmoker, presented with complaints of acute onset moderately severe intensity left sided chest pain after lifting heavy weight. Clinical examination was unremarkable. A chest radiograph was taken (Figure 1) which showed short left fourth rib. A computed tomography (CT) chest was done for further evaluation of same. Hypoplastic left 4th rib (short rib) was confirmed with no other pleuroparenchymal or bony abnormalities. Patient had no history of chest trauma and any surgery. It was an incidental finding and not a cause of his chest pain. He had a muscular cause for his chest pain due to heavy weightlifting which was relieved completely after 3 days of painkiller medications.

A short or hypoplastic rib is characterized by reduced anterior extension toward the sternum, often due to early fusion of the epiphyseal growth plate. This anatomical variation affects approximately 16% of the population,

with a higher prevalence on the right side, though it may also occur bilaterally. Typically, this finding is asymptomatic and isolated, with no clinical significance¹⁻³.

In some cases, however, short ribs can be associated with skeletal dysplasias, including thanatophoric dysplasia, achondroplasia, Ellis-van Creveld syndrome (chondroectodermal dysplasia), Jeune syndrome (asphyxiating thoracic dystrophy), and short-rib polydactyly syndromes. Awareness of these associations is important when evaluating patients with known genetic or skeletal disorders¹⁻³.

Figure 1. HYPOPLASTIC RIB (Short rib). A- Chest Xray PA View, B- three-dimensional reconstruction image of computed tomography chest; C- three-dimensional reconstruction image of computed tomography chest left lateral view. Showing hypoplasia of the left fourth rib (Black arrow).

REFERENCES

1. Sheflin JR. Short rib(s). *AJR Am J Roentgenol.* 1995 Dec;165(6):1548-9. doi:10.2214/ajr.165.6.7484610. PMID: 7484610.
2. Stanciu C, Daly-Devereux M, Tarrant A, Boyle MA. Isolated Hypoplastic left Rib Anomaly. *Ir Med J.* 2023 Oct 19;116(9):861. PMID: 37874492.
3. de Farias LPG, Menezes DC, Faé IS, de Arruda PHC, Santos JMMM, Teles GBDS. Anatomical variations and congenital anomalies of the ribs revisited by multidetector computed tomography. *Radiol Bras.* 2020 Nov-Dec;53(6):413-418. doi: 10.1590/0100-3984.2019.0131. PMID: 33304010; PMCID: PMC7720665.

*Assistant Professor,
Institute of Respiratory diseases, SMS Medical College, Jaipur.

Corresponding author:

Dr Ambika Sharma, Assistant Professor, Institute of Respiratory diseases, SMS Medical college, Jaipur.

Email: ambikasharma65@gmail.com

Mobile: +91-9930809241